

**THE ORETICAL AND TECHNOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF ORGANIZING AND MANAGING
LEARNER-CENTERED INSTRUCTION**

Ibrahimov F.

*Professor of Sheki branch of Azerbaijan State Pedagogical University
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0775-1048>*

Iskanderzadeh T.

*Sheki branch of Azerbaijan State Pedagogical University
Department of Natural Sciences and their Teaching Technology,
Researcher in Educational Theory*

Abstract

The article highlights that the challenges of the 21st century require the adoption of learner-centered instruction as an effective approach to educational practice. It identifies essential learner competencies, such as problem-solving and decision-making, as well as types of thinking, categories of knowledge and activity, and their application in task design, along with the development of metacognitive skills. The study further characterizes forms of work, instructional strategies, techniques, and methods in learner-centered teaching, in addition to learners' learning styles and the models and formats of this approach. Furthermore, it examines pedagogical and psychological approaches, including relevant theories and the creation of a healthy psycho-social classroom environment, which play a significant role in ensuring the effectiveness of learner-centered instruction, and provides a critical perspective on these issues.

Keywords: theory; learner-centered instruction; teaching strategies; methods; forms of work; instructional models; psycho-social environment; teaching and learning environment.

Relevance of the Study:

The characteristics of the 21st century (the contemporary era in which we live) require individuals to develop essential qualities for creative activity, including skills such as decision-making, problem-solving, independent learning, collaboration, teamwork, evaluating diverse perspectives, generating new ideas, and demonstrating initiative in a rapidly changing and evolving world. To achieve this, two key conditions must be ensured: 1) the existence of a process aimed at developing the qualities necessary for creative activity; and 2) the transformation of the individual into an active subject (agent) capable of organizing and managing this process in order to acquire these qualities.

In light of the above, it can be concluded that, in the present context, the existence of instruction aligned with "Education 4.0," corresponding to the "techno-democratic information society" as a foundational framework, is essential. Moreover, it is necessary for the learner to act as a subject in the organization and management of this process. Determining optimal ways of developing technological literacy, information culture, and intellectual skills, as well as regulating an educational environment that incorporates these approaches, is of critical importance. Despite this necessity, research in this area remains insufficient, and methodological systems for addressing pedagogically significant cognitive issues have not been adequately developed on a scientific basis. Based on these arguments, the relevance of the study entitled "Theoretical and Technological Aspects of Organizing and Managing Learner-Centered Instruction" is substantiated.

Purpose of the study: The aim of this work is to identify the directions of regulating the environment that affects the development of students' skills in the process of implementing general education in accordance with the challenges of modern society, in other words, the development of their technological literacy and information culture, intellectual skills. We hope

that this idea will give rise to hypotheses as a form of scientific cognition, which in turn will develop into a theory such as "Fundamentals of the Organization and Management of Student-Centered Learning", and a contribution will be made to "Didactics".

Methodological basis of the research. In the process of conducting the research, based on L. Bertalanfi's "Idea of System Analysis" [2;8] (the idea, which is explained as an attempt to study the properties of an object based on the properties of its parts - italics are ours - F.I), the "System-structural approach", which has been formed as an important branch of dialectics and has risen to the level of its alternative, empirical, empirical-theoretical and theoretical methods of scientific cognition, the internal relationships of the forms of scientific cognition, and various pedagogical and psychological research generalizations were used as a methodological basis.

Interpretation of generalizations from research materials: The Fourth Industrial Revolution is having an impact on the education system as well as on the socio-economic fields. Education, which is a process of sharing knowledge and experience of change, has developed in stages (including the specific characteristics of industrial revolutions) in accordance with the industrial revolutions. In the era of the Fourth Industrial Revolution, an Education system that can form a creative, innovative and globally competitive generation is required, and currently, the impact of the aforementioned revolution on the education process and the issue of "education of the future" are being discussed on various platforms and the necessary steps are being taken accordingly [11], [12; 92-97]. The expected paradigmatic changes in the education system and the implementation of global education reform have been further accelerated by the impact of the Fourth Industrial Revolution. [21; 147-171]

The Fourth Industrial Revolution has different implications for different areas of our lives. From this perspective, there are both opportunities and challenges for education. The use of different technologies such as IoT, 3D printing, Quantum computing, Artificial Intelligence, etc. allows for more effective information transfer and the development of a new “educational framework”.[14; 78-94].

It is necessary to distinguish two main reasons for the reforms carried out in the education system and its implementation system in connection with the challenges of the Fourth Industrial Revolution. The first is the training of a workforce with knowledge (information) and skills in accordance with the needs of a rapidly changing global economy, and the second is the establishment of an education and implementation system that can bring to the fore the productive forces (labor force) necessary for the development of an adequate information society during the industrial revolution. [9;288]

It is undeniable that education should adapt to the environment in which learners live and provide them with a secure and successful future. Intellectual and creative activity of everyone living in a “techno-democratic-information society” becomes a paramount requirement, and for this it is desirable that every member of this society rises to the level of a subject of intellectual skills, they must have information culture and technological literacy.

Information culture: is the knowledge, intellectual skills and habits necessary for a person to adapt to the information society; is the ability to use information resources and information communication tools of society; is the application of advanced achievements in the field of informatization and the development of information technology tools in society; is the ability to obtain and transmit information using modern technical means and methods, computer technologies.

Technological literacy is the ability of people to use various digital technologies, analyze information and operate safely in a digital environment. “This skill is not limited to using a computer and the Internet, but also includes: 1) Compliance with digital safety and cybersecurity rules; 2) Working with artificial intelligence and automation; 3) Digital analytics and data processing skills; 4) Using cloud technologies; 5) Quickly adapting to new technologies”[5]. Technological literacy includes the ability to use information and communication technologies.

Developing digital skills is essential to ensure that they can engage safely and effectively with digital technologies in the future. Education systems need to take a comprehensive and holistic approach, supporting all learners to develop the skills to be active and ethical users of digital technologies.[17; 57-79]

Digital education, allowing people to participate independently in social life. In addition, the reality of digital education and the digital revolution requires fundamental changes in the forms and methods of moral education, leading to the emergence of digital skills as the most important ability [16;58-64]. There is no doubt that the development of digital skills of learners will lead to their more active participation in society as digital citizens in the future. [15], [17; 57-79]

Due to the rapid development of technology, the knowledge and skills that students acquire during their education are outdated by the time they graduate. In order to help develop and shape the use of today's fastest-growing technologies in scientific and technical education, it is necessary to train students and prepare them for the digital environment. Adapting to a rapidly changing environment will make it necessary for students to stay in touch with educational institutions even after graduation, providing both workers with updated skills and young students (and faculty) with a new direction related to the rapidly changing realities of the industrial and corporate sectors.[18; 25-30], [19; 579-592]

In line with the “Techno-democratic-information society” that exists as a basis in the modern era, Education 4.0 uses unique technologies and tools to cope with these tasks and helps learners to develop themselves in accordance with changes in society. Therefore, Education 4.0 is a more realistic and practical learning approach that can provide high results for learners' learning. It is important to adapt to a rapidly changing world, and Education 4.0 is a system that educational institutions use to ensure this. This new system uses “smart” school management systems, learning management programs, communication tools, and teaching and learning tools.[13; 238-254], [16;3558-3564].

In the Education 4.0 approach, it has been determined that, going beyond constructivist education systems and Bloom's taxonomy, a teaching process based on the following areas will be applied: 1) 3R (Recalling, Relating, Refining) regulating understanding; 2) 3I (Inquiring, Interacting, Interpreting) encouraging research; 3) 3P (Participating, Processing, Presenting) based on drawing conclusions.[22; 92-98], [23; 40-45]

Education 4.0 is a “smart” and digital revolution for the benefit of all stakeholders in education. Education 4.0 introduces the best methods (methods) for teaching and reduces the administrative burden by automating many processes while modernizing these methods. In addition, it aims to increase the skills of educators and improve the learning outcomes of learners. [16;3558-3564].

The most important goal of Education 4.0 for all educational institutions is to motivate learners and improve their outcomes. By using technology, learners can better communicate with other stakeholders in the system, such as educators, management, etc. The learning outcomes of learners are directly proportional to the level of implementation of Education 4.0.[21;147-171]

Education 4.0 has the following features: 1) learning regardless of time and place (lifelong learning, e-learning, etc.); 2) the opportunity to receive personalized education according to the skills and abilities of students; 3) taking into account the suggestions of students when preparing the curriculum; 4) the priority of project-based learning; 5) the formation of skills to solve real-world problems; 6) the formation of students' ability to conduct analysis on big data; 7) the assessment of students' knowledge in the process of applying it to projects; 8) the transformation of new developing technologies into a part of the education system, etc. [11-12]

It is undeniable that there is a specificity in the appeals of each industrial revolution. This is manifested against the background of global changes taking place in the world, and at the same time it determines the existence of new shades in information culture and the content of technological literacy. At different stages of world history, humanity has faced serious changes and achieved results with the reforms carried out.

In order for students to demonstrate their skills and abilities in new areas emerging under the influence of the Fourth Industrial Revolution, it is necessary to implement fundamental changes in technology and the curricula of the subjects taught. By reviewing the curricula of the subjects formed on the basis of chemistry, biology, physics, etc., which are considered "basic sciences" in the new curricula, more attention should be paid to the teaching of computer science subjects, which play a key role in the formation of the Fourth Industrial Revolution literacy. Naturally, more attention should be paid to the teaching of the subjects in question. [20; 432-466]

Against the backdrop of the industrial revolutions, educational program developers had to seek answers to the following fundamental questions: 1) What knowledge, skills, and values should be reflected in educational programs?; 2) Will these knowledge, skills, values, and competencies form the necessary life skills in learners?; 3) How can the process of implementing education be made relevant and interesting for learners?; 4) How can assessment (an integral part of the process of implementing education) be made more productive and effective?

In our modern era, parameters such as relevance, practicality, effectiveness, and sustainability are the focus of attention as indicators of the quality of an educational program, while the indicator of its success is the quality of acquisition by learners and the extent to which learners can effectively use what they have acquired for their personal, social, cognitive, psychological, and emotional development.

UNESCO has the following criteria for a quality education program: the educational program must have clear objectives; meet the demands of today; be relevant to the current and future lives, experiences, desires and aspirations of learners; aim to build a prosperous future for learners in social and economic terms, taking into account the history and culture of the country in which they live; be fair and inclusive (taking into account the individuality and individual needs of learners, etc.); be learner-oriented (takes into account the needs of the learner, is appropriate to the age of the learner, helps in personal development and the formation of life skills, and does not overload learners); be open and flexible (integrates emerging innovations into the content); be consistent and relevant. [3; 5]

By the way, let us emphasize that the changes taking place in society are not possible only with the changes taking place in industry and technology. In parallel, the systematic implementation of changes and development in the superstructures that will guide the main dynamics of society - education, health, culture, etc. - is one of the main needs. Preventing the problems brought by the IV industrial revolution and preparing human resources that can compete on a global scale are

among the tasks facing the education system. This revolution is continuously affecting all components related to education, such as the structure of the curriculum, the development of the skills of educators, the inclusion of new technologies in the curriculum, and approaches to the implementation processes of education. In the era of the fourth industrial revolution, education must have potential opportunities that can develop society.

In learner-centered learning, the joint creative activity between the educator and the learner has the character of "subject \leftrightarrow subject" (S \leftrightarrow S), based on the paradigm of "opportunity \Rightarrow action \Rightarrow new quality", the educator performs the function of a facilitator, this process proceeds as the learner's research on the "learning problem". The inclusion of the learner as a main component in the learning system begins with the transformation of the goal formulated by the educator with reference to sound arguments into the goal of the learner.

In the aforementioned learning process, when the material to be mastered by the learner is perceived as the object of satisfying his cognitive needs, he directs (organizes and manages) the educational activity in an appropriate direction. This process is of a research nature and has the following components in its structure: educational situation (or tasks); 2) educational operations; 3) control; 4) price [1;150].

As can be seen from the presented structure, the student's educational activity begins with the solution of educational tasks.

By the way, let's comment on what is meant by educational tasks. Although its essence is reflected in the meaning of "task", its character is related to the meaning of "teaching". Educational tasks are distinguished from any scientific, military, sports, etc. tasks by one important feature. Educational tasks involve the discovery and mastering of general methods (principles, regularities) of solving various problems and specific practical exercises by students in their educational activities.

By presenting learning tasks, the educator, who performs the function of a facilitator, includes learners in a unique learning situation: in this situation, they become familiar with the content of general methods for solving learning tasks, taking into account all specific and concrete options, and acquire the appropriate knowledge, skills, and habits.

A system of special tasks is applied to form intellectual skills in students (determined by the requirements of the modern era). These tasks are designed on the principle of modeling the structure of various intellectual skills. As students complete them, they acquire intellectual skills such as determining the purpose of their work, systematizing educational material in this regard, independently collecting material, writing an essay, etc. From the point of view of the principle of developmental training, this method is considered effective. However, in order to use it purposefully, the system and content of intellectual skills in classes and subjects must be thoroughly developed.

Tasks and their system: should be consistent with the purpose of the lesson and aimed at solving the research problem set (according to the type of thinking, information sources, form of presenting results, etc.);

should be appropriate to the age, knowledge and intellectual level, abilities and interests of students, and should be differentiated; should be based on the state program and national values; should be relevant, related to real life and students' experiences; should be interesting, attractive, and encourage discovery; should be clearly stated; should contain clear and open questions.

It is possible for the learner to act in the position of a researcher when the content of the training material, the form of action of the means and methods (in the training process, the content of the training material, the means and methods act in place of the content, in relation to the organizational form) are in accordance with the research process. If we accept that the organizational form of training established in accordance with the research process has a unique structure, and this is reminiscent of the stages of the research process (in our opinion, by taking such a position, we would not have made such a serious mistake).

There are many specific features of educational tasks, but one thing is clear: in order to solve them, students must master the necessary educational operations. Educational operations are diverse. Many of them are of a general nature and are used almost equally in the mastering of various educational materials. Some educational operations are more typical for the mastering of certain educational materials (mathematical, linguistic, etc.). Educational operations applied in special cases are also distinguished. Intellectual processes - analysis, composition, comparison, generalization, etc. occupy a special place in the structure of educational operations. Intellectual processes are always implemented by applying them to the content of a certain subject (calculus, geometry, grammar, etc.) and "therefore appear in the form of various arithmetic, geometric, etc. operations". From this point of view, the formation of educational operations is directly related to the mastering of mental activity principles by students.

It is worth noting that human self-awareness has always been an urgent problem of world philosophy, psychology and pedagogy. Scientists have approached human self-awareness from the perspective of personality and have sought its roots in the process of forming a person's ideas about his own "I". Unfortunately, until recently, researchers have not sufficiently assessed a person's understanding of the characteristics of his own mental world, the world of thinking, and cognitive processes. In modern American psychology, this issue has been brought into the spotlight and has begun to be studied as a metacognitive system. It has been established that as children develop, certain ideas about cognitive (cognitive) processes are formed in them and they begin to regulate their mental activity. It is worth emphasizing that self-monitoring, self-regulation, self-assessment are metacognitive skills, which are related but different concepts. It is a person's awareness and understanding of his own cognitive processes.

Flavell studied and described in detail some of the functions of metacognition. The following can be noted among them: 1) Problem formulation and identification of possible solutions; 2) Knowledge of which cognitive processes are necessary for solving the task; 3) Activation of cognitive rules and methods; 4) Confidence in

the possibilities of thinking; 5) Attempt to solve tasks more efficiently. These functions are interconnected. The first function is conditioned by the formation of ideas about the goals of activity in children. As they grow older, they learn to apply known methods to various situations. Gradually, students develop ideas about cognitive processes. [1; 60], [7; 74]

Control also plays an important role in the formation of educational activity. The effectiveness of the activity is directly related to the level of control, as well as to the educational operations. Control is directly related to evaluation, which has an important feature as a unique component of educational activity. In the control process, not the final result of educational activity, but the results of individual educational operations are examined. In the evaluation process, the final result of educational activity is analyzed, and its compliance with the purpose of educational activity is determined.

When assessment is psychologically effective, it gradually turns into self-assessment, playing an important role in the formation of the learner's self-awareness; Self-monitoring, self-regulation, self-evaluation are metacognitive skills, which are related but different concepts. It is a person's awareness and understanding of his own cognitive processes; Self-monitoring consists of observing and following a person's actions, behaviors and cognitive processes during a task. Here, the learner does not try to control himself, does not judge or evaluate his own performance. He simply collects information about his performance by observing himself; Self-regulation is the ability of a person to control and manage his cognition, emotional state and behavior to achieve a goal. Its main components include: goal setting; planning; adaptation; Self-evaluation is the judgment or evaluation of his own activity or learning. Its main components include: evaluation; reflection; Self-monitoring is about observation and awareness, self-regulation is about actively managing cognitive and emotional processes to achieve goals, and self-assessment is about making judgments about and reflecting on one's own performance. Collectively, these are metacognitive skills that enable learners to become more effective learners by understanding and controlling their own learning processes.

Psychological research clearly shows that when educational activity is formed, the learner literally becomes the subject of his or her own activity.

In learner-centered learning, the main concern of the educator (facilitator) is to give special importance to the development of problem-solving skills in addition to the formation of cognitive skills of learners. Problem-solving skills are the ability to identify, analyze and solve problems efficiently and effectively. People with high problem-solving skills can evaluate situations, consider various options and choose the most appropriate way to achieve a solution. These skills are important in various areas of life, including work, education and daily decision-making. Also, problem-solving means facing new problems, finding a method and a successful solution to solve them. Correct problem-solving is applying the knowledge we have acquired to a problem we have never encountered before. This helps develop critical thinking and decision-making skills and prepares us to cope with some unlearned

situations in the future. For this reason, problem-solving is considered one of the essential 21st century skills. Properly teaching problem-solving not only benefits students' academic development, but also prepares them to succeed in an ever-evolving world where adaptation and collaboration are essential.[3;37]

In order to develop problem-solving skills in learners, the facilitator should focus on introducing them to problem-solving methods. An example of a cognitive action form that includes the following stages can be the substrate for the methods in question: 1) defining the problem; 2) planning a solution; 3) implementing the plan; 4) evaluating the process; 5) evaluation.

In the process of developing problem-solving skills in learners, the educator should focus on the need for them to have sufficient information about the various types of thinking, the analytical and heuristic logics of mental activity, and the integration of these into aspects of the unit.

It is known that thinking is a person's cognitive (cognitive) activity, a thinking process. During cognitive activity, a person's ideas, thoughts, and mental representations are formed or used. Thinking is a mental process that occurs in the brain that helps a person form psychological associations and various models. Thinking comes into play the moment a person starts thinking. Thinking is formed and develops during activities such as searching for information, processing it, grouping and generalizing these ideas to express them verbally or in writing to others, etc. Being able to think effectively is a skill in itself. In the teaching process, the facilitator must form the ability to think effectively in the learner. Depending on how a person thinks, there are different types of thinking and different forms of thinking: logical, critical, creative, convergent, divergent, verbal, non-verbal, deductive, inductive, analytical, etc. Instilling critical and creative thinking forms in learners creates conditions for their development. Therefore, each of these is very important in itself and needs to be formed during education. It should be taken into account that a person does not use only one type of thinking when thinking.

A critical thinker: correctly defines the problem; investigates the cause of the problem; collects information about the problem by investigating; processes and groups data and results; is able to solve the problem systematically; determines which solution is effective; tries to improve the solution to the problem; is able to detect inconsistencies and misunderstandings when reasoning; uses evidence correctly and impartially when justifying an opinion; is able to distinguish between logically sound and unsound ideas; sets aside judgment when there is insufficient evidence; is able to see the possible consequences of an action before doing it; is able to learn independently or at least has an interest in learning in this way; is able to see the difference between the acceptance of an idea by many and whether that idea is valid or not; is able to present different points of view without distorting, artificially exaggerating or ridiculing; accepts that his own opinions may be wrong, perhaps preferring personal preferences over evidence.

Creative thinking is a cognitive process that helps to look at objects, events, and problem-solving from a new and different perspective, a kind of "thinking outside the box." Creative thinking is not just about talent. It is a way of thinking that allows for different outcomes in different situations and different ways of solving problems.

When a person thinks creatively, they are able to solve difficult problems in a more appropriate, efficient, and different way, and they are able to look at things and issues from different perspectives. To do this, a person must have the ability to make connections between different concepts, draw analogies, and look at things from new perspectives.

To develop creative thinking in learners, it is necessary to repeat some activities frequently and develop skills in this direction. When these activities are applied together, they create the opportunity to look at problems and issues from a new perspective.

There are various techniques for developing creative thinking. The application and use of these techniques ensures the generation of ideas in the learner, solving problems in different ways, and ultimately a creative approach to the issue.

Information about various forms and models of learner-centered learning has been partially included in scientific sources. These include: 1) Synchronous and asynchronous learning; 2) Inquiry and research-based learning; 3) Problem-based learning; 4) Project-based learning (Project Based Learning-PBL); 5) Game-based learning, etc. Examples can be:

Here, in order to clarify the concept of "Different forms and models of learner-centered learning" and some of the considerations we have presented above, we consider it necessary to present a concise interpretation of the "Problem-Based Learning" and "Project-Based Learning" models.

Problem-based learning is a "learner-centered learning model." When introducing this model, learners are involved in solving real-life problems in accordance with the content of the subject. Effective learning is possible both in the context of using existing knowledge and acquiring new knowledge and skills. Thinking about a problem, discussing it thoroughly, and trying to solve it develops skills such as critical thinking, problem solving, and communication. Since problem-based learning is conducted in a group, it instills and forms cooperation skills in learners. At the same time, solving any problem and working for it activates their internal motivation and turns learning into a meaningful activity. Problem-based learning includes a number of stages. The stages in question are: 1) Presenting an open-ended question that expresses the problem; 2) Clarifying and discussing the problem; 3) Classifying knowledge (What do we know about the problem? What do we need to know about the problem?); 4) Suggesting possible solutions; 5) Sharing the results and the solution.[3; 93]

There are also experts who present problem-based learning as a subform of project-based learning with many features. Despite all their similarities, both have different features. Both project and problem-based learning models are learner-centered and have common

features in terms of creating learning activity in learners, developing critical thinking, problem solving, and cooperation. Unlike problem-based learning, the project-based learning model does not end with the acquisition of theoretical knowledge alone. It involves finding a solution to a problem using theoretical knowledge. Project-based learning is a model that reconciles the knowledge learned with their application and addresses real-life problems. At the same time, it allows for the development of skills such as collaboration, communication, and problem-solving during the process. In PBL, finding solutions to difficult and real problems is used for learners to learn various concepts and principles. The goal here is not for learners to learn and speak knowledge and facts as information, but to ensure that they are able to use this knowledge at the right time. The steps to be taken in project-based learning are: problem formulation; plan development; research and product preparation; scaffolding (providing the right direction) and monitoring; verification of results and evaluation of the process (activity). [3; 94-96]

It should be noted that the implementation of various projects in lessons and Project-Based Learning are not the same. In lessons, the implementation of the project is given to the students after the knowledge and skills are formed and then applied. In project-based learning, knowledge and skills are acquired during the implementation of the project. It is possible to apply project-based learning in all subjects. You just need to look at the issues from the perspective of the subject and think about what problem will be solved.

In the study of the theoretical and technological aspects of the organization and management of learner-centered learning, and in the generalization of the research materials obtained, we have accepted the need to keep the dialectical dependence "general↔specific↔exclusive" in focus as a necessary approach, and we consider it the right choice to consider it necessary to give importance to the aforementioned dialectical dependence in the application of the "Learner-centered learning model".

Pedagogical practice confirms that in the implementation of education, general pedagogical requirements should be expected on the basis of mutual cooperation between educators and learners in accordance with the "subject↔subject" principle. The requirements in question are: 1) completeness of the pedagogical process - educational, educational and developmental in nature; 2) creation of equal opportunities for learners - ensuring the same learning conditions for learners in accordance with the educational infrastructure of the institution, regulating the educational process taking into account the inclinations, interests and potential capabilities of learners; 3) personality orientation - developing the vital skills of learners based on their cognitive, communicative and psychomotor activities, and forming national and human values in them; 4) learner orientation - directing educational activities directly to protecting the interests of learners, meeting educational requirements, realizing their talents, and forming their personalities; 5) development orientation - implementation of complex measures that include the development prospects of students based on the results

obtained from the analysis of their educational achievements; 6) stimulation of activity - taking measures to monitor and evaluate the achievements of students in order to increase the efficiency of the learning process and increase their interest in learning; 7) creation of a supportive environment - providing the necessary infrastructure, a healthy moral and psychological environment, and creative and safe educational conditions to improve the quality indicators of education.

Based on the dialectic we emphasized above, we accept that in the implementation of education, based on mutual cooperation between educators and learners in accordance with the "subject↔subject" principle, general pedagogical requirements should be met (creatively) in accordance with specific conditions in the research, organization, and management of "Learner-centered learning".

Despite the stated approach, "Didactics" is considered a general term for "Theory of Education and Training", "If we assume that the theory of "learner-centered learning" (as the highest form of scientific cognition) is an interpretation in its special status, then the theories of "Multiple Intelligences" (Harvard Gardner), "Stages of Mental Development" (Jan Piaget), "Social Development" (Lev Vygotsky), "Thinking Style" (Karol Dweck), "Spiritual Development" (Lawrence Kohlberg), "Conditions of Learning" (Robert Gagne), "Emotional Intelligence" (Daniel Goleman), "Personality Formation and Development" ("Introverted and Extraverted Personality" - K. Jung) can only be considered as a higher form of spiritual learning about (some aspect, aspect, component of learning). Therefore, it would be in the interest of the general cause to refer to these theories (the latter) that we have presented in accordance with the specific conditions in the organization and management of "learner-centered learning" (creatively).

It is worth emphasizing here that the most important requirements that are guided by are the principles that arise from the "dialectical dependencies between wholes and parts" - regularities and laws - in the system to which they belong. These principles form the basis for the formation of the methodological system of teaching and determine its nature.

Scientific novelty of the research: The idea of "Theoretical and Technological Aspects of the Organization and Management of Student-Centered Learning" (considering that the idea is an important value) aimed at regulating the environment that affects the development of students' skills (the development of their technological literacy and information culture, intellectual skills) in the process of implementing general education in accordance with the challenges of modern society, has been defined, which, as a form of scientific cognition, will give rise to hypotheses, which, in turn, will develop into a theory such as "Fundamentals of the Organization and Management of Student-Centered Learning".

Theoretical significance of the study: The research on the presented topic has a specific function in directing further scientific activities for a broad study of theoretical and practical ways to solve the problem of creating conditions for sustainability for the future development of society.

The practical significance of the research is that in the real pedagogical process, practical educators have the opportunity to benefit from the idea of "Theoretical and Technological Aspects of the Organization and Management of Student-Centered Learning" in their practical activities, which is aimed at regulating the environment that affects the development of students' skills (the development of their technological literacy and information culture, intellectual skills) in the process of implementing general education in accordance with the challenges of modern society.

Conclusion. 1. The existence of information culture and technological literacy in every member of the society formed in accordance with the calls of the IV industrial revolution is a desirable quality; 2. The education system adequate to the "Techno-democratic-information society" has taken its place in scientific sources and pedagogical practice under the term "Education 4.0" and has been interpreted as a superstructure on logical grounds; 3. "Education 4.0", which exhibits an effective environment for the existence of information culture and technological literacy, has specific characteristics and it is possible to divide the skills that need to be formed in this system into groups on a certain logical basis; 4. At the stage of modern socio-economic development, intellectual and creative activity of everyone living in the "Techno-democratic-information society" has become a paramount requirement: 4.1. In order for a person to become a creatively active subject of that society, he (a person) must be surrounded by an educational environment that conditions the development of the necessary qualities; 4.2. In the "techno-democratic-information society", there must be an adequate training model for the implementation of education, which is formed as a superstructure; 4.3. In order to acquire the qualities corresponding to the demands of the base, the person (here - the student) must become an "enabler" of the function of an active subject of the organization and management of the implementation of education, which is formed as a superstructure; 5. In the implementation of education, general pedagogical requirements should be kept in focus based on mutual cooperation between educators and learners in accordance with the "subject↔subject" principle; 6. In the implementation of education, general pedagogical requirements formed on the basis of mutual cooperation between educators and learners in accordance with the "subject↔subject" principle should be anticipated (creatively) in accordance with specific conditions in the research, organization and management of "Learner-centered learning".

References

1. A.A.Alizadeh. Psychological problems of the modern Azerbaijani school. Baku: "Pedagogika", 2004. 432p.
2. Mirzajanzade AX Introduction to the specialty (Textbook for oil and gas profile higher schools), Baku, BSU Publishing House, 1990, 368p.
3. Methodology and pedagogy (A manual based on the updated framework document). Baku, Maximum Training Center, 2024.182p.

4. FN Ibrahimov, RL Huseynzade. Pedagogy. Textbook. In 2 volumes. Collection. Baku: "Mütarcim", 2013. 708p.
5. Elmira Mammadova. Technological Literacy: The Key to Success in the Digital World (tr.linkedin.com/posts/elmira-mammadova-01807722).
6. Feyziyev J.A., Ibrahimov FN, Bediyev S.R. Didactics (Textbook). Baku: Mutarcim, 2011, 624p.
7. General Psychology (edited by Professor AV-Petrovsky). Translation from the 2nd edition. Baku: "Maarif: 1977. 494p.
8. Z. Veysova. Application of new subject curricula at the general secondary education level. Baku: "Inkisha" scientific center, 2013. 163p.
9. Rasulov RA, Ibrahimov FN, Abdullayeva GA Sheki branch of the Azerbaijan State University of Physical Education in 30 years: successes, prospects. Baku, "Mütarcim", 2022. 502 p.
10. Schwab, K. The Fourth Industrial Revolution; World Economic Forum: Geneva, Switzerland, 2016; ISBN 97819448350020.
11. World Economic Forum Report (2016 b). New Vision for Education: Fostering social and emotional learning through technology. http://www3.weforum.org/docs/WEF_New_Vision_for_Education.pdf.
12. Vichian P. Education 4.0: New Challenge of Learning // St. Theresa Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences, 2016, Vol 2, No. 2 pp. 92-97.
13. Wilkesmann M. Wilkesmann U. "Industry 4.0-organizing routines or innovations?"// VINE Journal of Information and Knowledge Management Systems, 2018, Vol 48, No. 2, pp238-254.
14. Christian K. Challenges and Opportunities for Education in the Fourth Industrial Revolution // African Journal of Public Affairs, 2019, Vol 11, No. 3, pp. 78-94.
15. Sari L., Arif S. The Roles of Digital Literacy, Technology Literacy, and Human Literacy to Encourage Work Readiness of Accounting Education Students in the Fourth Industrial Revolution Era// International Conference on Economics, Education, Business and Accounting, 2019.
16. Priya S. Digital Revolution of Education 4.0// International Journal of Engineering and Advanced Technology (IJEAT), 2019, Vol9, No. 2, pp. 3558-3564.
17. Mascheroni G., Olafsson K. The mobile internet: Access, use, opportunities and divides among European children// New media and Society, 2016, Vol 18, No. 8, pp. 57-79.
18. Ercan Ö. Development of New Directions in Education and Education 4.0//University Research Journal, 2018, Vol 1, No. 1, pp. 25-30;
19. Ling Li. Education supply chain in the era of Industry 4.0// System Research and Behavioral Science. 2020, Vol 37, No. 4, pp. 579-592.
20. Fatih D., Elif I., Nurdan K. Educational Program 4.0 from the Means of Realizing the Targeted Transformation in Higher Education// Bayburt Faculty of Education Magazine, 2019, Vol 14, No. 8, pp. 432-466.

21. Abdullah D. Changing education training paradigms from industrial 4.0 to education 4.0//International Congress on Social Sciences //(INCSOS 2018 Quds). 2018, Vol 13, No. 15, pp. 147-171.

22. Hussin A. Education 4.0 Made Simple: Ideas For Teaching// International Journal of Education and Literacy Studies, 2017, Vol 6, No. 3, pp. 92-98.

23. Dario A., Alessandro C., Marta F., Elpido R. Smart education in the context of Industry 4.0 // IEEE Global Engineering Education Conference(EDUCON), 2019, pp.40-45.